

Book of Leviticus

By John Mellison, University of Texas, Austin

Entry tags: Hebrew Bible, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Israelite Religion, Text, Jewish Traditions

The book of Leviticus is the third book in the Pentateuch (the first five books of the Hebrew Bible). It consists of 27 chapters and much of the content is Yahweh's instructions to Moses at Mount Sinai. Leviticus takes place within the larger story that narrates the Israelites' escape from Egypt and journey into the Promised Land. In Leviticus, Yahweh gives instructions to Moses, and Moses repeats the instructions to the Israelites. This material includes: laws concerning sacrifice (for priests and non-priests), details concerning the priesthood, issues of ritual purity/impurity, and exhortations and instructions for living a holy life. The dating of Leviticus has proved to be challenging, as the book makes no reference to outside historical events. Consequently, there is no clear consensus regarding the date of its composition. However, the book does bear signs of literary growth and development indicating that its composition likely happened in several stages.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 400 BCE

Region: Levant, Sinai Peninsula

Region tags: Israel, Middle East

Levant

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Milgrom, Jacob. *Leviticus*. Continental Commentaries. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2004.
- Source 2: Levine, Baruch. *Leviticus*. JPS Torah Commentary. New York: Jewish Publication Society, 1989.
- Source 3: Noth, Martin. *Leviticus*. Old Testament Library. First Series. Translated by J. E. Anderson. Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1965.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/acref/9780195046458.001.0001/acref-9780195046458-e-0434>
- Source 1 Description: "Leviticus" in *The Oxford Companion to the Bible*
- Source 2 URL: <https://www-theologyandreligiononline-com.ezproxy.lib.utexas.edu/encyclopedia-chapter?docid=b-9780300261905&tocid=b-9780300261905-19830&pdfid=>
- Source 2 Description: "Book of Leviticus" in *Anchor Yale Bible Dictionary*

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/online-bibles/biblia-hebraica-stuttgartensia-bhs/read-the-bible-text/>
- Source 1 Description: Original Language: Biblia Hebraica Stuttgartensia (BHS) from Academic Bible
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/the-new-oxford-annotated-bible-with-apocrypha-new-revised-standard-version-2018>
- Source 2 Description: Translation: The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha, New Revised Standard Version

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Notes: Possibly parchment as well.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The field agrees that the book shows signs of literary growth and redaction over a period of time.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– Field doesn't know

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– Yes

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: The oldest copy of Leviticus was found among the Dead Sea Scrolls in Qumran cave 11 as part of a textual archive. The scroll has been dated between the late 2nd century BCE and the early 1st century CE.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The field generally agrees that the book of Leviticus reflects the interests of priests and not a king

or the state. However, it is unclear the extent to which the scribal apparatus needed to produce texts might be funded by the polity.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: Yes; however, the term "scripture" or the notion of a canon is anachronistic for the period the texts were produced in.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Notes: Scholars agree that the texts have been altered throughout their literary growth and redaction process, but the fact that Leviticus is cast as Yahweh's words to Moses suggests that alterations were avoided.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There was likely a group of people trained to transmit these texts—and we see examples of this among the Qumran manuscripts—but the field does not have enough evidence to get a clearer picture than this.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: The book of Leviticus becomes canonized as part of the Hebrew Bible, but around the time of the text's production the notion of "scripture" did not exist.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: However, different religious communities include different works in their canon.

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the cannon as it is currently understood?

– No

Notes: The history of interpretation is very important for some religious communities.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: When Leviticus was written, there is not any evidence that its audience was actively proselytizing, though later audiences would. However, there are numerous commands in Leviticus to fairly treat outsiders who dwell with the Israelites.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In general, no. However, many scholars hold the view that Leviticus is roughly made up of two sources that have been joined together—chapters 1-16 and 17-26. In this view, the later source is seen to rework and reform the earlier work, although scholars disagree about which portion came first.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In the text, Yahweh gives commands to Moses, Moses relays the instructions to the people, and the people carry out the instructions. Many of these instructions are concerned with proper ritual actions. Later religious communities read this text aloud, but the field doesn't know if any portion(s) of Leviticus may have been read aloud as a ritual practice or during another ritual practice (e.g. a sacrifice).

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The evidence from Qumran suggests that people were not concerned by different versions of the same text. There is a Hebrew version of Leviticus (the Masoretic Text) as well as a Greek translation, and the Greek translation may have been translated from a different Hebrew Vorlage.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Yes; however, the term "scripture" or the notion of a canon is anachronistic for the period the texts were produced in.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: Not at the time the text was written. The term "scripture" or the notion of a canon is anachronistic for the period the texts were produced in.

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The text is largely cast as Yahweh's instructions to Moses on Mount Sinai.

– Yes

Notes: The text is largely cast as Yahweh's instructions to Moses on Mount Sinai.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Notes: The place of the text in the canon has not been shifted, but different religious groups emphasize different texts.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Ritual manual

Notes: The text lists various rituals (ritual list) and also includes instructions for various rituals (ritual manual).

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

Notes: The notion of a legal "code" has been problematized as well as the exact nature of these "laws" in Leviticus. Scholars are divided as to whether these laws were actually used but portions of Leviticus are clearly cast as law codes.

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This continues to be a matter of debate with strong opinions on both sides.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Lunar?

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

Notes: Leviticus does have instructions about planting but they are not tied to a calendar.

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

Notes: Leviticus does have instructions about harvest but they are not tied to a calendar.

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– No

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

Notes: Leviticus does have instructions about lending practices but they are not tied to a calendar.

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

– Specify: Annually

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

– All members

Notes: The text seems to imagine all Israelites participating in the festivals and feasts, but this is not completely clear.

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

– number: The field doesn't know.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Pilgrimages?

– No

↳ Feasting?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Perhaps; in Leviticus 19:27-28, the Israelites are forbidden from various acts on behalf of the dead. Also, in Leviticus 10:1-7, Moses gives instructions for bringing two dead men out of the camp, leading scholars to speculate that burials may have had time and/or location constraints.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: For example in Lev 26:31, Yahweh is threatens to not smell the Israelite's pleasant-smelling offerings. In Lev 1:1, Yahweh appears to dwell in the tent/tabernacle.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: In Leviticus, Yahweh is primarily concerned with cultic purity: the Israelites keeping themselves pure and Yahweh's tabernacle being pure. Yahweh speaks to the Israelites exclusively through Moses. In Lev 9:23-24, the glory of Yahweh appears before the people and fire comes from Yahweh and consumes an offering.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text is not clear here. However, the very notion of offering sacrifices to a deity is tied to the idea that the deity needs to be fed regularly.

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life
– Yes

↳ In dreams
– No

↳ In trance possession
– No

↳ Through divination practices

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: In Leviticus, Yahweh speaks with Moses. Yahweh speaks to other people (prophets) in other portions of the Hebrew Bible, but only to Moses in Leviticus.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Leviticus specifically forbids divination (Lev 18:21, 20:2-6).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred space(s)
 - Yes
- ↳ Sacred object(s)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Yes
- ↳ Adultery
 - Yes
- ↳ Incest
 - Yes
- ↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].
 - No
- ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
 - No

- ↳ Other sexual practices
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
 - Notes: Leviticus 19:32 gives instructions to respect elders.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
 - Notes: Other texts in the Hebrew Bible possibly do, but Leviticus does not.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done by other entities or through other means
 - No
 - ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - Yes

Notes: In Leviticus 10:1, for example, two men are struck by the deity for improper ritual action.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– No

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Yes

Notes: Many of these are detailed in Leviticus 26.

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?
– No

↳ Political failure?
– No

↳ Defeat in battle?
– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?
– No

- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - No
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - No
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - Yes
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: There are promises of rewards in the text (as in Leviticus 26), but they are not yet realized in the text's conception.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that cleanliness in Leviticus is for the sake of cult purity.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

Notes: Leviticus 18 and 20 prohibit men from sexual activity with a variety of different partners: various family members, a woman and her daughter, menstruating women, an animal, a neighbor's wife, and another man who is already the sexual partner of a woman. For centuries, this last prohibition (in 18:22) was thought to refer to pederasty. It is only in the last century that it has been interpreted as a prohibition against homosexuality. See Bruce Wells, "On the Beds of a Woman: The Leviticus Texts on Same-Sex Relations Reconsidered," in *Sexuality and Law in the Torah*, eds. Hilary Lipka and Bruce Wells (New York: T&T Clark, 2020), 123-58.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Notes: Leviticus 18 and 20 prohibit women from sexual activity with animals.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: Leviticus 11 lists which animals may or may not be consumed, though it is not clear if the prohibited foods were necessarily desirable.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Notes: The text gives instructions for dedicating property and valuable items to the temple, but it does not require it. Further, frequently throughout Leviticus are instructions for sacrifices and offerings.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Leviticus 23, for example, gives instructions for celebrating various feasts and convocations at regular intervals.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– I don't know

Notes: The text frequently describes prohibitions or laws as "statutes" or "commandments." Leviticus 20:22, for example, instructs the Israelites to keep the the statutes and commandments of Yahweh so that the land does not vomit them out. However, these commandments are about cultic purity and loyalty to Yahweh, and not so much about ethics.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Notes: However, Yahweh promises to drive away the out-group members (the "nations") so that Israel can possess their land. The Israelites are prohibited from acting like the nations (doing abominable things) and they are instructed to drive away fellow Israelites who break certain rules.

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

Notes: However, it is limited to very specific phrases. For example, the Israelites are referred to as the "children of Israel" throughout.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: Human sacrifice is specifically forbidden.

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

Notes: There are places where material offerings are mandatory. For example, Lev 27:30 dictates that 1/10th of the produce of the land be given to Yahweh. Throughout, though, there are instructions for how various material offerings (produce, grain, oil, animals, etc.) are to be made, but these sacrifices are not always mandatory.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, the text (e.g. Lev 27) gives instructions for dedicating valuable items like land, people, or houses.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Animals, grain, oil, produce, etc.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: The smells of various sacrifices and offerings are described as a "pleasing aroma" to Yahweh.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it required?

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance)?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff?

– Yes

Notes: In Leviticus 6:9-13, the priests are instructed to keep a continual fire burning on the altar outside of the tabernacle. Leviticus 24:1-9 gives some instructions for Aaron to maintain the Tabernacle. However, Leviticus does not give a complete answer on this topic, though other texts in the Hebrew Bible prescribe who is to maintain the sacred space.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Segmentary Lineage

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The text of Leviticus was likely composed by priests. The reproduction and final form of the text was likely produced by people from one tribe (Levites) and/or scribes (who may have been from different tribes).

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: The responsibility is placed upon individual Israelites in Lev 25:35-38.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: In Leviticus 19:9-10, the Israelites are instructed to leave the gleanings and the crops at the corners of their fields for the poor and the stranger.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– Yes

↳ Does the text require the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes?

– Yes

↳ Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is taxation linked to an understanding of charitable giving?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: The text mentions animals that are not to be eaten, and the proper procedure for slaughtering and eating an animal (e.g. not eating the blood). However, the text does not discuss how food should be produced.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Book of Leviticus, Milgrom, Jacob. Leviticus. Continental Commentaries. Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2004.

Reference: Book of Leviticus, Levine, Baruch. Leviticus. JPS Torah Commentary. New York: Jewish Publication Society, 1989.

Reference: Book of Leviticus, Noth, Martin. Leviticus. Translated by J. E. Anderson. Old Testament Library, First Series. Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1965.